

A Comparative Study of the Role of Identity in the Persian Translation of English Political News

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Abstract

Translators have always imposed their own stances and identities upon the texts they are translating. This manipulation is of primary importance when it comes to critical texts such as political ones. The concept of identity is the core one to all translations. Farahzad (2012) proposes that a thorough and careful analysis of (non)linguistic features can help the translation critic identify changes in Target text (TT) which is ideologically driven. This study, therefore, aims at comparing translations of English news, identifying the identity modifications. Then, an attempt is made to justify and explain the results in terms of CDA in order to see the rationale behind the choices. To this end, 100 pieces of the recent political news (from 2016 to 2017) were collected. When all the data had been collected, the original texts – political news – were studied and analyzed along with their translations into Persian in order to identify the implications of translators' choices in terms of CDA. The next stage was discussing the results in terms of CDA. In this final stage the researchers attempted to reveal the ideological position -identity- of the translator in his/her decision making. The results of the study were significantly revealing; out of 100 pieces, 79 news items were directly indicative of the ideology and identity of the translator.

Keywords

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), Identity, Political news.

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Introduction

Newmark (1988) believes that translation has a crucial role in transmitting culture and making connection between different countries with different language and culture. In addition, translation is defined by Catford (1965, p. 20) as “the replacement of textual material in one language (SL) by equivalent textual material in another language (TL)”. However, translation is never neutral; translators impose their own stances and identities on the texts they are translating. This manipulation is of considerable importance when it comes to serious texts such as political texts, in which different strategies are employed to change the point of view as it is desired. As Venuti mentions, “there is a common assumption that national identities are homogeneous, often grounded in biological, ethnic or racial considerations and manifested in a particular language and culture” (2005a, p. 177).

Alvarez and Vidal (1996) enumerate some factors which constrain translators:

Translators are constrained in many ways: by their own ideology; by their feelings of superiority or inferiority towards the language in which they are writing the text being translated; by the prevailing poetical rules at that time; by the very language in which the texts they are translating is written; by what the dominant institutions and ideology expect of them. The translation itself will depend upon all of these factors (p. 6).

Whatever the reason, the concept of identity is the core one to all translations. Translation defines new identities. Translation is where the power relations between languages are revealed (Tymoczko & Gentzler, 2002).

According to Joseph (2009, as cited in Eriksson, 2009, p. 6), identity is who we are. The paradox of identity is that on the one hand, it is about ‘sameness’; what we have in common with other groups, like being Swedish or Christian and so on, but, on the other hand, identity is about being unique; what sets us apart and the inimitable part of our self. According to Joseph (2004 as cited in Eriksson, 2009, p. 6), “Social identity is the part of us that identifies itself with a larger

group. Our identity is connected to this certain group since we share values, ideas and knowledge with this group” (p.79). Moreover, Joseph (2004, as cited in Eriksson, 2009, p. 6) defines personal identity as “an individual’s concept of self, or who I am for myself and enacted identity is how our identity is expressed through language and communication; how we are seen by others” (p. 81). It can be argued that our personal identity and our enacted identity will never meet; they are forever set apart since it is impossible for us to know who we are for others just as it is impossible for others to see how we see ourselves inside. However, we will always try to imagine how we are seen by others. In that way, enacted identity is associated with our personal identity. This relation between our personal identity and the enacted identity highlights how important our language is to our identity since our enacted identity is expressed through language.

According to Venuti (1995a), follow-up developments, especially in modern translation studies, created an interdisciplinary field thereby broadening and revitalizing the translation studies. In the 1980s, translation studies witnessed a huge shift from the linguistic-laden approach which previously had a large number of advantages for the translation studies.

Problem and Purpose

Schäffner and Bassnett (2010) claim a large number of texts are related to political topics. These texts (political news) involve comments, which have a particular role to play. These genres do not simply report on political events in a neutral way, but they provide evaluations and thus can have an impact on public opinion about politics and also national identity. Translation also plays a very important political role in international policy-making and diplomacy. Language can affect a nation and its individual identities, as well as its relation with other countries (p.12). As Aranda (2010) states the concept of identity is often regarded as a bridge between national territory and identity, space with which each individual identifies. The dominant identity and norms of a community would reflect in its

translations and the choices the translator makes during the process of translation.

According to Hermans (1985, p. 101, as cited in Farahani & Arbabi, 2016) claims "from the point of view of the target literature, all translation implies a degree of manipulation of the source text for a certain purpose". Manipulation scholars reject the traditional idea that the target text is a faithful reproduction of the source text. But rather it is a reflection of translator's identity. As Dukate (2007, p. 89) states (as cited in Farahani & Arbabi, 2016) "the Manipulation School represents an approach to translation as manipulation or more precisely as rewriting of texts for a specific target audience in conformity with target language norms and under various constrains". In other words, translation is affected by the target identity. Gentzler (2002) believes that translation is an open door to a new a world in that it enables people to enter a translated world that is, a translation facilitates the opportunity to learn about a new culture and its people.

As Yifeng (2012) states, texts do not stay intact during the process if translation. Consequently, translation has the potential to transform and shift identity, which is often brought about by acceptance of social norms, birth, and cultural factors. Therefore, further research is needed to shed some light on identity concept in translation studies and elaborated some of the common strategies utilized by translators to render this concept. There is an unbreakable link between meaning and identity and this is why translation is highly influenced by ideology. The idea is that during the process of translation, the identity-related effects manifest themselves in translated text. Translators may keep the impact of identity of the source text or may impose another preferred identity. This study tends to study how much a political text is affected by the translator's identity (if any).

Significance of the Study

Political news, more often than not, represents the identity stamp of media which generate them. The identity as a concept plays a deciding element in the decision making involved in political discourse translation. It can impact on the translation as well (van Dijk, 2000).

In order to make the issue clear, the present research attempts to lay a foundation for a far and clear understanding of the identity as a concept in recent political news.

The present study tries to have profound implications for translators and translator trainers so that they should not be viewed as neutral agent but should be considered as social actors who impose their ideologies upon the texts they translate and, hence, may change the identity of the ST. Furthermore, the results of the present study could identify and reveal the growing need and requirement for raising translators and readers' awareness of the importance of being careful about the inseparability of language and identity in translation, and every word and grammatical structure translators choose may show some identity points of view.

According to Tymoczko and Gentzler (2002) translation is not simply an act of faithful reproduction but, rather, a deliberate and conscious selection, assemblage, structuration, and fabrication – and even, in some cases, of falsification, refusal of information, counterfeiting, and the creation of secret codes. In these ways translators, as much as creative writers and politicians, participate in the acts that create knowledge and shape culture.

According to Bassnett (2002) media plays an important role in the transmission of information about politics and political events from other countries; this study is seeking to find out the common implications in terms of identity. That is, without media, there would not really be any politics and international relations. In order to do so, the STs and TTs are placed side by side and compared to see translators' choices. Then these choices are justified in terms of CDA".

Therefore, this study aims at comparing translations of English news, identifying the identity modifications. Then an attempt is made to justify and explain the results in terms of CDA in order to see the rationale behind the choices. The rationale for carrying out this research lies in the well documented findings in the literature that most translators find the concept of *identity* to be difficult to translate. The identity concept does not only play a critical factor in the decision

making involved in the translation of political discourse, but it can also manipulate the translation. To clarify the issue, the proposed research tries to provide a foundation for understanding the concept of identity in political news.

Research Questions

The following questions guided our study:

- Q1.** Does the identity position of political news change as a result of modification made during the process of translation?
- Q2.** To what extent translators' choices reflect their identity?

Theoretical Framework

As for the theoretical framework of the research, Farahzad's model for CDA (2012) is adopted in order to explore implications of translational choices which reflect the identity of the translators, in other words, to reveal the ideological standing of the translator. The model examines translational choices made by the translator, and analyzes them in the light of critical discourse analysis (CDA) to identify identity implications.

Research Design

This study aims to identify the common implications in terms of identity issues. It is a descriptive, qualitative, and explanatory research based on the Farahzad's three dimensional model for CDA (2012) of political news broadcasted in English and Persian websites. Since the data derived from the corpus are explained and discussed. Qualitative research methodology was employed in the present study due to the nature of the study and certain characteristics that are associated with qualitative research methods.

Farahzad's CDA Model

The advocates of the Manipulation School maintain that all translation involves a degree of manipulation. Lefevere (1992) accentuates the importance of investigating the manipulative aspect of translations by claiming that "the study of the manipulation processes of literature as

exemplified by translation can help us towards a greater awareness of the world in which we live." (p. vii). Manipulation in translation may be witnessed at the level of identity.

Therefore, the present study was conducted to examine identity manipulation as distortion of political news. It aimed to find out the identity-related political items which are most commonly manipulated in the translation of news. It also attempted to determine the extent to which translators' choices reflect their identity during the process of translating the news.

In her 2012 model, Farahzad differentiates between translation quality assessment and translation criticism which she divides further into comparative and non-comparative. She also attempts to explain the ST and TT relationship in terms of intertextuality. Farahzad's model is essentially based on a critical discourse analysis point of view, in which, incorporating the idea of inter-textuality, she makes an attempt to propose a framework to capture the ideological changes in the process of translation. She proposes an analysis of texts at the three levels namely textual, para-textual and inter-semiotic.

The first level – textual level – is further divided into vocabularies and grammar. The latter in turn can include passivization, nominalization, positive/negative, verb tense and re-ordering of sentence elements. Translation strategies are also among changes at textual level, as Farahzad believes, which can reflect translators' ideological standing. Farahzad proposes that a thorough careful analysis of the above-mentioned (non)linguistic features can help the translation critic to identify changes in TT which is ideologically driven.

Therefore, as it can be seen every grammatical or lexical choice made by the translator can be a reflection of their ideology, this includes the application of translation strategies. Euphemizing and derogating as two general translation strategies are also employed by a certain purpose in mind.

Corpus of the Study

The translator needs to make some changes according to their

viewpoint. Consequently, during the process of translation, sometimes the original is manipulated due to the identity and ideological differences between the source and target language, political system and religious norms of the target language, or the good of the viewers, which is of course decided by authorities. Accordingly, it can be said that changes in identity is part and parcel of translation. However, it appears that little attention has been paid to the identity-change aspect of translation. Therefore, the present study looks for identifying the implications of translators' choices in terms of CDA. The present study intends to unmask the changes – conscious or unconscious – that happen during the process of translation, and see the consequences of these changes on the presentation of ST and /or TT identity. In order to achieve its goal sufficient political news are needed. Therefore, the corpus of the study consists of 100 political news collected from 2016 to 2017. The news was put side by side with translation into Persian.

Procedures

In order to collect the data 100 political news from Fars News Website – from 2016 to 2017 -were gathered. When all the data were collected, the original texts – political news – are studied and analyzed along with their translations in order to identify the implications of translators' choices in terms of CDA. The next stage is discussing the results in terms of CDA. In this final stage the researchers try to reveal the ideological position -identity- of the translator in his decision making.

Data Collection

Since this study tends to elaborate on identity-driven texts, the best framework to analyze the data was found to be those presented within the area of Critical Discourse Analysis. Thus, this study focuses mainly on the macro level and attempts to find the motivations behind translational choices. The main focus of this research is to study “identity”. In order to investigate the influence of identity on

translation, 100 political news from English and Persian websites were randomly selected. Persian news was taken from Fars news Agency and English news was taken from various news agencies including: Al-Monitor, Foreign policy, DW, etc. Out of these 100 news certain excerpts, including identity, political lexemes were chosen with their Persian translations.

In this study, some identity concepts were selected, extracted, and analyzed based on the CDA principles. The researchers focus on the words, phrases, and sentences that included identity lexemes. Although the sentence is commonly taken as the unit of translation and analysis, the researchers assumed that the unit of comparison should not be limited to the sentence level.

Results

Why America and Israel are The greatest threats to peace. آمریکا و اسرائیل بزرگترین تهدید علیه صلح هستند.

The very first example is a clear one in which, according to Farahzad, there is a reordering in the sentence. The original English version, in fact, has a question tone which is turned into a strong statement in the Persian version. This grammatical change reflects the anti-US identity of the Iranian translator. Another example with the same strategy and with much stronger effect (a question into statement):

Is the State Department trying to cover up for its own negligence that cost four Americans, including the American ambassador to Libya, their lives on **September 11?** به نظر می‌رسد وزارت خارجه آمریکا دارد تلاش می‌کند تا بر اشتباه خود که موجب کشته شدن ۴ آمریکایی، از جمله سفیر آمریکا در لیبی، در **سالگرد** ۱۱ سپتامبر شد سرپوش بگذارد.

Again according to Farahzad's terminology one can witness what is called positive/negative change. In other words, the negative sentence in the English text is rendered into a positive sentence. However, it is not a positive/negative change which is significant by itself; it is the motivation behind the change which is of great importance for CDA.

This change along with other vocabulary changes aim at exaggerating the identity stance of the translator who seeks to criticize the ‘unreal’ world.

Also:

Concern among Senators has now risen to bipartisan levels.	اکنون دیگر نگرانی در مجلس سنا به یک حزب خاص محدود نمی‌شود.
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This is another example where there is a change in point of view (positive to negative or vice versa).

Also:

On that basis, Obama should reject any efforts to impose a rigid, predetermined timetable on his diplomatic efforts on Iran.	به همین خاطر، رئیس‌جمهور آمریکا <u>نباید</u> هیچ چارچوب زمانی معین و محکمی را برای پایان روند دیپلماتیک با ایران ارائه دهد.
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This is the reverse of what Farahzad call nominalization and which can be called verbalization. This process increases the subjectivity power of an action in a sentence, which shows how the translators support this ideological view.

Also:

We agreed not to address broad questions about the United States’ commitment to nuclear nonproliferation that would be raised by a U.S. decision to use force against Iran.	توافق کرده‌ایم درباره تعهد آمریکا به پیمان منع گسترش سلاح‌های هسته‌ای بحث نکنیم؛ اگر آمریکا <u>تصمیم بگیرد</u> برای جلوگیری از تولید سلاح هسته‌ای به ایران حمله نظامی کند.
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In her modal, Farahzad (2012) also recognizes that the translation strategies translators employ can reflect being identity-based. Here the addition of the adjective واضحی (which means clear) reduces the strength of the original sentence. This may be indicative of the translator’s reluctance to agree on the proposition.

Also:

The true threat of nuclear proliferation is that it can deter American aggression.	خطر اصلی در گسترش <u>سلاح‌های</u> هسته‌ای این است که از جنگ طلبی آمریکا جلوگیری می‌کند.
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And another interesting case of addition:

CIA Created Afghan Heroin Trade	سی آی ای تجارت مواد مخدر را در افغانستان و پاکستان به راه انداخت.
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Here there is the addition of an adjective in the translation completely absent in the original version. The addition of such words is highly indicative of translator's attempt to take side and make his identity visible in the text.

And another example where the translator omits a negative adjective which they see as opposing their ideology:

The latest round of fighting broke out after Palestinian terrorists fired an anti-tank missile at an Israeli jeep patrolling the Gaza-Israel border on November 10, wounding four soldiers.	علت آخرین دور از این درگیری‌ها، حمله فلسطینی‌ها با یک موشک ضد تانک به جیب سربازان اسرائیلی در تاریخ ۱۰ نوامبر بود؛ در حمله به این جیب نظامی که در مرز غزه با سرزمین‌های اشغالی گشت می‌زد، ۴ سرباز اسرائیلی زخمی شدند.
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Another case of adding complete new information to the TT to grant some sort of authenticity to the statement:

According to the Morsi camp, the politicized Court intended to dissolve the Consultative Council (the upper house) and the Constitutional Assembly	کمپین مرسی معتقد است همان‌گونه که فضا دادگاه قانون اساسی علناً اعلام کرده‌اند ، این دادگاه سیاسی می‌خواهد شورای مشورتی (مجلس علیا) و مجمع قانون اساسی را نیز منحل کند.
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Another case of addition with the aim of imposing the TT ideology:

In Yemen, al Qaeda in the Arabian Peninsula exploited the fall of Ali Abdallah Saleh's dictatorship to take over remote parts of the south and east of the country.	در یمن، گروهک القاعده در شبه جزیره عربستان، از سقوط دیکتاتوری علی عبدالله صالح برای به دست گرفتن کنترل بخش‌های دوردست جنوب و شرق این کشور استفاده کرد.
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This is one of the most obvious examples in which the identity of the translator manifests itself. The word Israel being translated as

refers to a strong anti-Israel viewpoint which is assumed by Iranian identity.

In another piece of news:

Egyptian President Mohammad Morsi called Israeli airstrikes in Gaza "unacceptable" and withdrew Egypt's ambassador to Israel .	محمد مرسی رئیس‌جمهور مصر، حملات هوایی اسرائیل علیه غزه را «غیر قابل قبول» خوانده و سفیر مصر را از سرزمین‌های اشغالی فراخواند.
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Farahzad sees re-ordering of sentence elements as having ideological implications which reflect the identity of the translator.

Another example where the reordering of the sentence elements changes the emphasis of the sentence:

When their missiles are tipped with warheads carrying nuclear, biological, or chemical weapons, even weak regional powers have a credible deterrent regardless of the balance of conventional forces.	حتی قدرت‌های ضعیف منطقه‌ای هم اگر بتوانند به کلاهک‌ها و سلاح‌های هسته‌ای، بیولوژیکی و یا شیمیایی دست پیدا کنند، صرف‌نظر از توان نظامی متعارف، می‌توانند از این سلاح‌ها به عنوان بازدارنده‌های قوی استفاده کنند.
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Also:

The Chinese are particularly worried that their supply of oil from the Persian Gulf, mostly transported to China by sea, could be disrupted by the U.S. Navy .	مقامات چین از این نگران هستند که نیروی دریایی آمریکا ممکن است تصمیم بگیرد شریان انرژی چین را که از خلیج فارس تأمین می‌شود و عمدتاً از طریق دریا انتقال می‌یابد، قطع کند.
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Another way in which, according to Farahzad, translators manifest their identity is passivization/ activization. The original passive sentence is translated by an active statement which puts more responsibility on the US officials.

Use of a positive word:

Nevertheless, the Arab nations of the Persian Gulf are allied to the United States, whereas the Islamic Republic is the only major Middle Eastern power isolated from the West.	اما نکته این‌جا است که کشورهای عربی خلیج فارس با آمریکا متحد هستند، در حالی که ایران تنها قدرت بزرگ منطقه‌ای در خاورمیانه و مستقل از غرب است.
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Another case of using euphemistic words:

حماس بیت المقدس و تل آویو را هم مورد حمله موشکی قرار داد. این دو شهر که تا کنون از حملات موشکی فلسطینی ها در امان بودند، اکنون با استفاده حماس از موشک های دوربردی که احتمالاً از لیبی یا ایران وارد غزه شده اند، رنگ تهدید را به خود می بینند.	Hamas has launched rockets at Jerusalem and Tel Aviv, cities previously immune from such attacks but now under threat as Hamas uses the longer-range rockets in its arsenal, likely smuggled into Gaza from Libya or Iran.
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In this piece some part of the original statement is omitted, which results in keeping the core meaning and reducing the harsh tone in the original attributed to Iran.

Another example of omission:

در این میان، دو مطلب مهم وجود دارد که باید درباره آنها جستجو کرد. اولاً، کمبود اطلاعات و مقدمات لازم امنیتی برای پرسنل آمریکا در یکی از نقاط به شدت خطرناک و ناپایدار جهان.	There are two issues of grave importance to be investigated here. The first is the disastrous lack of intelligence and proper security arrangements for U.S. personnel in a highly violent and volatile part of the world.
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Again here we shall refer to Farahzad who emphasizes that every single change may have ideological motivation pushed by the identity of the translator.

«کریستوفر استیونز» سفیر آمریکا در لیبی در دفتر خاطرات خود، که به دست خبرنگار سی ان ان منتشر شد، از جان خود ابراز نگرانی کرده است؛ احساسی که مسلماً مراتب بالاتر از وی هم آن را داشته اند.	According to Ambassador Christopher Stevens's diary discovered by a CNN reporter, he feared for his life, a fact he would surely have shared with his superiors.
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This example serves to show how some decisions may be reflecting the identity of the translator, but not necessarily ideological and/or political. Here the translator, assuming the identity of their own community, sees it necessary to add some information which may not be known to the receptor audience.

Another good example:

Yet another letter to the State Department was circulating on the Hill yesterday, according to the Washington Examiner, among all the members of the Senate Foreign Relations Committee, including chairman John Kerry (D-MA).	به گزارش «واشینگتن اگزمینر» نامه دیگری نیز دیروز در مجلس سنا به امضای همه اعضا کمیته سیاست خارجی مجلس سنا، از جمله «جان کری» رئیس کمیته و نماینده دموکرات ایالت ماساچوست، رسیده است.
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And another example containing omission:

Renewed violence broke out between Israel and Hamas last week, with three Israelis and some 120 Palestinians being killed over the course of seven days from Gaza rocket attacks and targeted Israeli airstrikes, respectively.	هفته گذشته بار دیگر درگیری نظامی بین اسرائیل و حماس از سر گرفته شد؛ در حملات موشکی حماس و حملات هوایی اسرائیل، ۳ اسرائیلی و حدود ۱۲۰ فلسطینی کشته شدند.
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And:

Indeed , the declaration protects presidential decrees from judicial review.	پیش‌نویس پیشنهادی مرسی نظارت قوه قضائیه را بر اعمال رئیس‌جمهور لغو می‌کند.
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A case of adding some information absent in the ST:

Increasingly, drones are attacking AQAP in the deserts of Yemen	روز به روز حملات پهبادی بیش‌تری در بیابان‌های یمن علیه القاعده در شبه جزیره عربستان صورت می‌گیرد.
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In this example, containing a grammatical change – namely replacing a pronoun for a noun, as well as using an emphatic word – one can see a huge increase in the responsibility put on the shoulders of the West.

Thomas Donnelly of the American Enterprise Institute and the New American Century Project has long been crystal clear that this is the real reason for opposing Iranian nuclear capability	«توماس دانلی» عضو اندیشکده مؤسسه آمریکن اینترپرایز و «پروژه قرن جدید آمریکایی» مدت‌ها است به وضوح می‌گوید که دلیل مخالفت ما با هسته‌ای شدن ایران همین است.
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Again the example reveals how the addition and omission of single words leads to a change in the tone of the sentence. And the translator uses this strategy to his benefit to impose their own identity on the discourse, by taking side and revealing their position to the news.

This **perceived** threat from Iran seems overstated given **Israeli military superiority on Iran.** به نظر می‌رسد مقامات اسرائیل این تهدید را بیش از حد بزرگ کرده‌اند.

Here is an example where a completely different statement is given in the translation, given the fact that the translator – as an Iranian – does not want to confess the superiority of another country to their own. This reaction is part of what forms the identity of a translator.

Another example of a thorough change in the meaning:

The Israeli war **rhetoric** against the **Islamic Republic** of Iran should be interpreted as a way to pressure the U.S. and its European allies to strengthen the economic sanctions regime **targeting** the Iranian nuclear program. **تهدید** اسرائیل به جنگ علیه ایران را باید تلاش این رژیم برای فشار به آمریکا و متحدان اروپایی‌اش جهت افزایش تحریم‌های اقتصادی با هدف تضعیف برنامه هسته‌ای ایران دانست.

Using stronger and more negative words as referring to the Other, i.e. the group seen as not in agreement with the ideology and identity of the translator, is another strategy to make internal integration.

Also:

It is an accident of fate that the **quadrennial** American exercise in selecting a president happens to coincide almost precisely with the anniversary of the 1979 seizure of the **U.S.** Embassy in Tehran. سرنوشت این‌گونه رقم خورده که انتخابات ریاست‌جمهوری آمریکا دقیقاً با سالگرد اشغال سفارت **این کشور** در تهران در سال ۱۹۷۹ مقارن شود.

In the same way:

By April 1979, a **full** seven months before the **much-ballyhoed** Soviet “invasion” of Afghanistan, US officials were meeting with corrupt Afghan warlords and oligarchs bent on **overthrowing** Taraki. تا آوریل ۱۹۷۹ و هفت ماه پیش از «حمله» شوروی به افغانستان، همان مقامات آمریکایی که بعدها این حمله را شدیداً محکوم کردند، خود با فرماندهان و مقامات فاسد افغان دیدار می‌کردند تا بتوانند ترکی را از مقام خود ساقط کنند.

This is an example where the translator uses a structure to pose more doubt on the statement. All these changes of the level of certainty regarding a certain issue are not accidental. Given a certain political issue, a translator commissioned to work for a special community with certain ideology and identity may have a quite different viewpoint from another community. This difference is manifested in the process of translation through very single choice by the translator.

And another example of a statement with a different level of certainty:

The **stated** purpose of the operation is to reduce Gaza terrorists' rocket-firing capabilities and to deter them from attacking Israel.

اسرائیلی‌ها هدف از عملیات خود را تضعیف توانایی‌های موشکی حماس و جلوگیری از حمله این گروه به سرزمین‌های اشغالی توصیف کرده‌اند.

And:

Clearly direct talks can help reduce tensions on the ground and might help to manage the conflict, **if not to resolve** it.

واضح است که مذاکرات بین دو طرف ممکن است بتواند تنش‌ها در منطقه را کاهش دهد و شاید به مدیریت بحران (و یا حتی حل آن) کمک کند.

Here again the translator uses more emphatic words to pose a tone with more stress, which leads to higher level of certainty in the target text.

And:

For most of its existence, AQIM had been confined to kidnapping Westerners traveling in the remote deserts of Algeria, Mali, Mauritania, and Niger and other criminal enterprises.

فعالیت‌های القاعده در مغرب اسلامی اغلب به ربودن **شهروندان غربی** در بیابان‌های دوردست الجزایر، مالی، موریتانی و نیجریه و یا دیگر اعمال مجرمانه محدود بوده است.

Also:

Back in Pakistan, the old al Qaeda leadership, what jihadists call al Qaeda al Um or "mother al Qaeda" is rebuilding.

شاخه قدیمی القاعده در پاکستان که جهادست‌ها آن را «القاعده مادر» می‌خوانند، **اکنون در حال بازسازی خود است**.

And another purposeful omission on the part of the translator:

While the benefits of our hyperconnected communication systems are undisputed, they could potentially enable the viral spread of information that is either intentionally or unintentionally misleading or provocative.	با وجود این که فواید نظام ارتباطی بین‌المللی در جهان امروز غیر قابل انکار است؛ اما این ارتباط ممکن است موجب انتشار اطلاعاتی شود که خواسته یا ناخواسته گمراه‌کننده و گاهی تحریک‌آمیز و مضر است.
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The first generation was the original band in Afghanistan created by Osama bin Laden in the 1990s. The second emerged after 9/11 when the group resurfaced in Pakistan and then across the Muslim world. Now a third iteration can be discerned in the wake of bin Laden's death and the Arab Awakening .	نسل اول القاعده گروهی بود که در دهه ۱۹۹۰ به دست اسامه بن لادن در افغانستان تشکیل شد. نسل دوم بعد از حوادث ۱۱ سپتامبر در پاکستان به وجود آمد و سپس وارد کشورهای اسلامی شد. اکنون نسل سوم این گروهک را می‌توان پس از مرگ بن لادن در کشورهای بیداری اسلامی مشاهده کرد.
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When we are talking of ideological or identity changes in a text through the process of translation, we must not necessarily be looking for big notorious omissions, additions or any other change easily detectable by one reading. Some changes are at the level of a single word or a simple re-ordering. In this example small but key choices by the translator indicate his/her identity. The choice of **گروهک** which shows it is not seen as a rightful independent organization. The change of Arab Awakening into Islamic Awakening which clearly shows the translator's identity as an Iranian.

Also:

Using the cover name Jabhat al Nusra, al Qaeda has become perhaps the most lethal element of the opposition to Bashar al Assad's brutal dictatorship	این گروهک با نام «جبهه نصرت» به یکی از جدی‌ترین عوامل شورشی علیه حکومت بشار اسد تبدیل شده است.
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A very clear example of identity-reflecting choices is the simple omission in the following example:

The U.S. invasion of Iraq also worked to **predominantly** Shiite Iran's advantage, providing Tehran the opportunity to expand its regional influence by playing the sectarian card.

حمله آمریکا به عراق همچنین به سود کشور شیعی ایران تمام شد و فرصتی را در اختیار تهران قرار داد تا در بحبوحه درگیری‌های فرقه‌ای، نفوذ منطقه‌ای خود را افزایش دهد.

A good example that reflects the cultural identity of an Islamic community is the one above. Here a more general term is used to refer to makeup items; since it is not common to talk about these items in details in public media.

Discussion

The results of the study were significantly revealing. Seeking to find the extent to which the identity of the translator is reflected in the process of translation, the present study analyzed 100 pieces of recent political news. Out of 100 pieces, 79 news items were directly indicative of the ideology and identity of the translator. The model based on which the present study was conducted was that of Farahzad (2012). Almost all the items Farahzad mentions as identity-reflecting items were identified in the corpus. These include: The textual level divided into vocabularies and grammar. The latter can include passivization, nominalization, positive/negative, verb tense and re-ordering of sentence elements.

Also translation strategies are also among changes at textual level, as Farahzad believes, which can reflect translators' ideological standing. As the analysis revealed almost every single choice (and/or change) the translator makes leads to the reflection of their cultural, political, social and even religious identity. At the level of vocabulary, the use of stronger or weaker, more general or more specific, more euphemistic or more derogative etc. words was highly indicative of the fact that the translator was trying to impose their own identity as a member of a specific community. Similar to what van Dijk(2000) mentions were identified in the process of the analysis of the present corpus:

Positive self-presentation

Van Dijk (2000) calls this a kind global strategy with the aims of providing a positive representation of inner-group i.e. the group of which the translator is a member. This is similar to euphemism used in the present study.

Negative other-representation

This is another global strategy which is complementary to positive self-presentation. According to van Dijk's (2000), this strategy is realized by the use of derogatory terms and focusing on the Negative characteristics of the outgroup members (p. 78). This is similar to examples of the use of more negative words used in the present study.

There were cases in which the (political) texts were deliberately manipulated; and the corpus also included many cases for the use of translation strategies or any other discursive strategy (as proposed by Farahzad). It is not unusual that the addition and/or omission of a single words can change the stress of a whole sentence or even effect the point of view in a piece of news altogether. The general effect of all types of changes is that the identity of the translator manifests itself.

As it was mentioned the data analysis section of the present study revealed significant information concerning translation strategies as well as other discursive strategies as valuable tools at translators' disposal, different ways they are employed, the way a CDA-based approach can unmask translators' intentions – ideological or non-ideological- and the way single choices made by translators can add up to affect the entire text. All this said, one can assert that translators' identity is like their fingerprint which can be seen in every process of translation.

Looking from a critical discourse analysis point of view we can see the reason behind every single choice made by translators. One can clearly see that the discursive strategies (including translation strategies, changes in grammatical and vocabulary choices) are highly ideologically loaded, which are indicative of the identity of the

translator. Perhaps the main conclusion to be drawn is that translators used various choices to impose – consciously or sub-consciously – their own identity. The translators have different identity background; therefore, they try to represent the same issue based on their own interest, an interest which is representative of their own identity. This may have happened consciously or sub-consciously. In addition, the findings of the present research revealed the importance of grammatical and vocabulary choices in this process.

In order to answer the questions, after extracting the identity-reflecting sentences and putting them along with their translations, the researchers analyzed the data based on a CDA approach to find identity implications and changes found in the study because of the identity of the translator. Each original sentence was compared carefully with its translation.

The answer to the first research question is: yes. As the analysis of the data revealed the identity position of political news changes as a result of modification made during the process of translation.

It can be claimed that translators (as members of communities) possess multiple identities. These include cultural, social and even religious. Identity works as a motivation behind choices that translators make. These choices may be conscious or sub-conscious. As Farahzad(2012) points out in her model, the areas where the ideology/identity of the translators resurfaces are the grammatical and/or vocabulary choices they make. Translators attempt to represent their own community as justified and rightful, and that is why they use different words from that of the ST.

Texts, especially critical texts like political news, are laden with items which reflect the identity of their writers/translators. These items are the structures they use, the vocabulary choices (among others) they make, the translation strategies they employ. Therefore, the addition or omission of an item may be because of its agreement/disagreement with the identity of the translator.

The answer to the second research question needs a little more

explanation. The researchers found the role of translators in representation of ideological inclinations of great importance. If the researcher wants to quantify the answer, the analysis of the data revealed that 79 out of 100 items were clearly imposed by the identity of the translator. This means that rarely does it happen that news items pass without change.

News items come from all around the world. This, in practice, means that they carry the identity of the text producers. This identity may not necessarily be in agreement with the identity of the translator. Therefore, the result is changes in viewpoint of the text.

Conclusion

The present research taking a Critical Discourse Analysis approach described the relation between the use of language and the representation of identity inclinations. In order to analyze the manifestation of identity inclinations, by drawing upon CDA, the researchers selected one of the forms of media which is political news. The concepts of ‘Self’ and ‘Other’ came from post-colonial literature to the discussion about immigration literature. In post-colonial literature ‘Self’ is superior to ‘Other’. Whatever belongs to ‘Self’ is positive, superior and good and whatever belongs to ‘Other’ is negative, inferior and bad. Therefore, translators are always trying to present their own identity as good and the others’ identity as bad. Continually they compare the identity of the ‘Self’ with the identity of the ‘Other’, representation of ‘Self’ and representation of ‘Other’ (see van Dijk, 2000). As it was expected, and as the discussion demonstrates all cases of discursive changes – including grammar, vocabulary, as well as translation strategies – were at the service of identity of the translator. In other words, all the detected manipulations work to impose a positive representation of the identity to which the translator belongs. The same discursive strategies (vocabularies, grammar, passivization, nominalization, positive/negative, verb tense, reordering of sentence elements, and,

translation strategies) are employed to convey a different identity from that of the ST, either in favor of Self or against the Other.

Discourse Analysis can be used in many fields of life. Also, it is a new field, so it is worth mentioning its profits and pedagogical implication for translation studies, translator trainees, translators. Fairclough (1995) affirmed that “Critical language study and critical language awareness can...be reflexively applied within educational organizations to the practices of such organizations. Accordingly, such reflexive work could involve learners and teachers in analysis of and possible change in their own practices, as speakers and listeners (and viewers), writers and readers” (p. 227).

References

- Alvarez, R. & Vidal, M. (1994). *Translation power subversion*. Adelaid, Clevedon, Philadelphia: Multilingual Matter.
- Aranda, L. V. (2010). *Dis/placing territories of identity in translation*. Retrieved from: www.entreculturas.uma.es/n2pdf/articulo01.pdf
- Bassnett, S. (2002). *Translation Studies*. London: Routledge.
- Catford, J. C. (1965). *A linguistic theory of translation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Eriksson, A. (2009). Identity, language and culture in Eva Hoffman’s lost in translation, Mid Sweden University.
- Farahani, M. & Arbabi, M. (2016). Manipulation in drama translation. *International Journal of Research Studies in Language Learning*, 5 (4), pp. 83-94.
- Farahzad, F. (2012). Translation Criticism: A Three-dimensional (model based on CDA). *Translation Studies*, 9 (36) pp. 27 - 44.
- Gentzler, E. (2008). *Translation and Identity in the Americas: New Directions in Translation Theory*. New York: Routeledge.
- Lefevere, A. (1992). *Translating, rewriting and the manipulation of literary frame*. New York: Routledge.
- Newmark, P. (1988). *A Text book of translation*. London: Prentice Hall.
- Schäffner, C., & Bassnett, S. (2010). *Political discourse, media and translation*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.

- Tymoczko, M., & Gentzler, E. (Eds.) (2002). *Translation and power*. Boston: University of Massachusetts Press.
- Van Dijk, T. A. (2000). *Ideology: a multidisciplinary approach*. London: SAGE Publications.
- Venuti, L. (1995). *Translation and the formation of cultural identities*. New York: Routledge.
- Venuti, L. (1998). *The scandals of Translation*. New York: Routledge.